

INTERNAL NATION BRAND EQUITY OF BANGLADESH: CONCEPTUALIZATION AND MEASUREMENT

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Abstract

The study first attempts to design an integrated model which may help in evaluating the nation and next measures the brand value of Bangladesh. Equity measure was assessed at four distinct levels for both Non-Resident Bangladeshi (NRB) citizens as well as Resident Bangladeshi (RB) citizens, termed as, Dimension variable, Wellbeing variable, Component variables, and Utility variables. Results indicate that there is ample scope for improvement and at the same time, it is also apparent that the perception of NRB differs that from the RB regarding various utility factors. Also, results indicate that the Bangladesh brand equity of internal populace is higher compared to results depicted by global indices. At the macro dimensional levels, the statistical difference between the three dimensions; relational, subjective, and material were undertaken. Though the equity perception of citizens is better than the global perception scores for Bangladesh, however, the scores for economic wellbeing and social wellbeing is significantly lower compared to natural wellbeing and human wellbeing. The final analysis was at the micro level with 36 variables termed as the utility variables. The strengths of Bangladesh comprise of a total of 12 (33%) variables, mediocre performing variables constitute 17 (47%) variables, while the concern areas encompass 7 (20%) variables. One other major finding at the utility level is the, pollution management, lack of media positivity, and public trust. These three implies that the first requires changing mindset and practices of the population in general to create a physical evidence of a clean nation. The second requires the media to be more responsible in portraying the nation, research has clearly outlined many positivity of the nation which must be outlined and communicated to the population at large. The third is a direct outcome of the second, lack of trust on the nation. This is where a serious drive to focus on the basic concept of 'Nation First' must be embedded across all levels of the citizenry.

Keywords : *Bangladesh, Brand Equity, Internal Nation Brand Equity, Internal Nation Brand Equity Measurement.*

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1. INTRODUCTION

The origin of the word brand can be traced to marking of ownership by farmers to identify their stock (Bastos et al., 2012). The first presence of animal seals dates to the Bronze Age, in the Indus Valley Civilization, presently South Asia (Moore et al., 2008). Today, brand is associated with both tangible and intangible value and is considered as the ultimate equity of an entity, be it, at an individual or a nation. The primary purpose of transforming a product into a brand emerges from the objective to translate an offering into trust (Anwar, 2018), which is expected to ultimately ensure wellbeing of humankind. Thus, it is much beyond the traditional concept of branding, which focused on trade mark or a symbol by earlier scholars (Butler, 1914). Branding pioneer Walter Landor states “products are made in the factory, but brands are created in the mind.” Thus, Brand is a fundamental entity in marketing to ensure societal wellbeing and translate reality into perception.

The growth of product branding to branding individuals and place branding resulted in the creation of success stories of product branding. Dolores coined place branding as endogenous marketing process that integrates social, economic, environmental, and technological dimension of a society with a focused intent of maximizing benefit to stakeholders through meeting their needs (Dolores et al., 2013). Nation Branding, coined by Simon Anholt first noticed the importance as well as the effects of nation branding and stated, “nations have become far more cognizant of the value of their brand as an asset” (Teslik, 2007). He referred to this as a systematic process of aligning the actions, behaviors, investments, innovations and communications around a strategy for strengthening competitive identity of a nation.” (Anholt, 2008). Wally Olins, one of the most acclaimed country branding specialists in the world, who also happened to be the only globally acclaimed specialist to have advised the state government of West Bengal in India, and reflected on Bangladesh as well, states, “A product is rationally similar (to another) but emotionally different. Also, it’s about profit and pushing up its share margin. It has to be effective immediately.” A nation on the other hand has an audience — both internal and external. “There’s tourism involved as well as investment. You must gauge if you can be effective over 25 years.” (Ikafafeng, 2010).

The emergence of the modern concept of Nation Branding theory can be traced in the fusion of two distinct concepts community and society, which interestingly, are considered as antonyms by many (Tonnies, 1957). Over the years, three distinct components of community have been characterized. First and perhaps the foremost is ‘consciousness of kind’, which is the intrinsic shared consciousness about things, it is more than shared attitude or perceived similarities (Gusfield, 1978). Second, is the presence of shared rituals, social solidarity, and traditions. The third being, sense of moral responsibility that results in the shared responsibility and obligation towards the society (Marshal, 1994). Society on the other hand has been characterized as the outcome of modernity and commercial growth resulting in more depersonalized, mass produced, globalized, and less grounded type of humane experience (Lasch, 1991). Today, in this highly competitive globalized world, the concept of nation

branding has gained immense momentum (Dinnie, 2004). Countries are competing to attract the attention, respect and trust of investors, tourists, consumers, donors, immigrants, media and the governments of other nations.

This psycho-behavioral dimension of people in general, perhaps, has resulted in the belief that brands are built to portray target markets' experience through touching their emotions that is derived from the culture they represent; thus, creating a passion within the target market for the brand. One must however understand that the souls of every individual are driven by their own heritage. All brands are tangible entities plus values and associations that ignite passionate advocacy among people since it is depicting the cultural values they trust and go after. It is therefore evident that any exercise involving nation branding must operate within the general definition of a 'nation'; a large group of people of similar race, language, and experience. Thus, nation should not be considered as a product in the conventional sense. A nation does not offer a tangible product or service only; instead, it represents and encompasses a wide variety of macro and micro factors and associations that essentially results in generating an experience. These factors could include people, policies, location, heritage, environment, economy, beliefs, language, education, communication, global relations, etc. It is evident that this diversity may evoke a dynamic and more complex picture of a nation. More specifically, it may result in a paradox.

The paradox in the conceptual framework of Nation Branding is explained by delineating certain specific framework that explains the overall concept. One must understand that nation branding is not a propaganda but is based on perception regarding a nation. It is entrenched in our mind; we throw together a whole lot of attributes, positive and negative, about countries and we think about them in terms of simple narrative which ultimately converts into belief. We all do that irrespective of our level of intelligence. These perceptions may not be real but based on global communications regarding the nation and peer or personal experience. Thus, it is vital to segregate the concept of communication and propaganda while developing a nation brand strategy. Communication is effective when there is a demand for the information focusing on a unique core value that is treasured by the society being targeted. Propaganda on the other hand works only under unchallengeable authority or if one has total control over the mind of the audience and never contradicted (Anwar, 2010). Thus, nation brand must have wants, interests, and demands. This results in nation brand image, that is perception or intangible element of the brand; and nation brand identity, which is the tangible element of the brand. Nation branding as an operational strategy is basically good housekeeping (Dinnie, 2015).

Based on the discussions outlined above, one of the definitions of nation branding can be outlined as the following. "Nation Branding is concerned with a country's whole image on the international stage, covering political, economic and cultural dimensions; nation branding goes beyond the narrower purpose of country-of-origin or place brands to promote specific economic interests." (Fan, 2010). Annholt (2002) on the other hand outlines, "globalization is turning the world into a gigantic

supermarket, where countries compete to capture mind and market share of exports, tourism, foreign direct investments and immigration⁹. Thus, it is evident that nations are perceived first by their own citizens and second by other publics around the world, the combination of which ultimately results in what is called the nation brand. Figure 1 shows that the success of a nation is reflected in the beliefs of their own people first and that is translated to the world through media to rest of the world (Keller, 2003).

The global brand image of Bangladesh over the last decade has been around the second quartile to third quartile amongst the list of nations in terms of ranking. In FutureBrand Country Brand Index, for example, Bangladesh ranked 50th amongst the top 75 nations by population size and GDP (Brand Finance, 2010). On the other hand, in the Anholt GfK Roper Nation Brand Index, where 60 top nations among 200 nations are evaluated, Bangladesh is not amongst the top 60. In East-West Nation Perception Index, Bangladesh ranked 77th out of 200 nations (East West Communications, 2019). In Good Country Index, which is rated as one of the best general indices, Bangladesh ranked 105th amongst 169 nations in 2021 (Good Country Index, 2021). In Soft Power Index, Bangladesh ranked 78th out of 105 nations in 2021, although Bangladesh did well in economy and COVID management (Bhuiyan, 2021). In Brand Finance ranking, which also considers soft power, Bangladesh ranked 35th among 100 nations; this is primarily due to good economic performance (Brand Finance, 2021). The Legatum Prosperity Index (2021) on the other hand placed Bangladesh in 126th among 167 nations. One very important aspect that requires mention is the overall percentile score of Bangladesh has hovered around the 50-percentile mark. The global rating clearly shows great variations, probably due to the differences in measures and methodology. In addition, one needs to keep in perspective that these are all external perception of Bangladesh, which may or may not have been influenced by experience of individuals, media and word-of-mouth molded by both nonresident Bangladeshi citizens and entities. However, clearly, perception of internal public, citizens of Bangladesh has not been rated till date.

Figure 1 : Conceptualization of Nation Brand Image

2. NATION BRAND EQUITY MODELS

The concept of Brand Equity was first introduced into the business literature in 1980 which resulted in the Brandz model by Millward Brown. The first official definition

of Brand Equity was published in 1989 by Peter who defined it as “the added value endowed by the brand to the product”. The conceptualization of Brand Equity measurement was first published by Simon and Sullivan (1993). The theory was however popularized by Aaker (1991).

While discussing issues relating to nation brand equity, the two most prominent thought leaders of the concept of nation brand, Simon Anholt and Wally Olins, placed the following argument while assessing nation brand equity measurement. Anholt argues that “throughout the twentieth century, most of the really successful international brands have come from countries that are successful brands in their own right, and substantially transfer of imagery and brand equity can often be seen to occur between the two” (Anholt, 1998). Olins (2002), while discussing on the complexity in understanding and measuring nation brand equity concludes, “it is not the concept that people in general detest so much while evaluating nation brand equity, as the word brand, which appears for some people, to have trifling and superficial implications unworthy of the national idea”. Though both have strongly focused on internal as well as external stakeholders’ perception and ground realities of the nation, however, they could not arrive at a singular unbiased and globally acclaimed definition (Rashid, 2013).

Originally, Kotler and Levy identified the potential of researching on nation brands as a marketing effort and building separate theoretical model from the traditional business concept (Harengel et al., 2014). Eight major and most mentionable models can be outlined while measuring brand equity of nations or countries. Interestingly, all these measures have emerged in the private sector domain rather than the academia. They are, Future Brand Country Index (FBCI) (2019), Anholt GfK Roper Nation Brand Index (RNBI) (Feinberg, et al., 2021), Country Brand Strength Index (CBSI) (Fetscherin, 2010), East West Nation Brand Perception Index (NBPI) (East West Communications, 2019), Good Country Index (GCI), Global Soft Power Index (GSPI) (Yavuzasian, et al., 2016), Brand Finance Nation Brand Index (BFBI) (Haigh, 2020), and The Legatum Prosperity Index (LPI).

The conceptual model of the eight indices outlined below have been restructured to help develop a standard guideline for further analysis. However, the basic conceptual framework has been maintained. It needs mention however, that all proponents have time and again outlined the bias associated with developed nations. Moreover, since the weightage assigned are dependent on perception of individuals, developed nations clearly are rated higher. In addition, the nation brand is faced with two diametrically opposing forces, the distinctiveness of the country for unique positioning at the same time being assessed on some common global standards which are set by the developed nations. The paradox is that many unique features are being identified, which may not be enough to create an impression based on the global standards or even worse, may not be considered while undertaking global measures (Fan, 2006). Thus, at one level, the global audience have a certain degree of knowledge and experience about a nation; while at another level, each country has her own cultural values that are decoded with entirely differing perception and belief (Roth, 1995).

2.1 The FutureBrand Country Brand Index (FCBI)

The model was developed by the FutureBrand Team. FCBI measures the strength of perception of countries around the world in the same way as one studies consumer or corporate brands. The five factors considered are quality of life, environmental friendliness, products and services, polarizing politics, and business potential and tourism. Figure 2 depicts the conceptual framework of the FCBI model.

Figure 2 : FCBI

2.2 Anholt GfK Roper Nation Brand Index (RNBI)

This is one of the earliest models measuring nation Brand Strength by the Father of Nation Brand Concept, Simon Anholt. The index was developed to help governments, organizations and businesses, comprehend quantify and ultimately create a strong nation brand image and reputation. The RNBI measures the power and quality of each country’s “brand image” by combining six dimensions; people, culture & heritage, investment & immigration, tourism, exports, and governance as depicted in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3 : RNBI

2.3 Country Brand Strength Index (CBSI)

The model was conceived by Mark Fetscherin and attempts to measure country's effort to build and manage its brand framed primarily by the behavior of its domestic stakeholders and factors that has become an essential part of a country's sustainable development. The CBSI helps to assess nation brand value through objective measurement rather than survey perceptions. It helps governments with a tool to measure the strengths of a country brand, identify any weaknesses to help revisit the country brand strategy since countries need to build, manage and protect their brand. The nation brand factors outlined under CBSI are depicted in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4 : CBSI

2.4 East West Nation Brand Perception Index (NBPI)

This model was designed by East West Communications. The concept suggests that it is difficult for countries to address their branding and communications problems if they don't know where their strengths and weaknesses lie. Thus, the model utilizes an indirect measurement methodology using a third party, neutral, whistleblower observation approach. It makes an educated guess as to how a country is viewed by the world, based on news clippings, surveys, focus groups and the like, introduced by the local and global media and media personalities. The East West Nation Brand Perception Index is based on analyzing millions of mentions of countries in hundreds of thousands of news articles, every quarter.

2.5 Good Country Index (GCI)

This is the most recent model developed by Simon Anholt and Robert Govers. Good Country Index does not measure what countries do at home; rather, it aims to start a global discussion about how countries can balance their duty to their own citizens with their responsibility to the wider world. The model uses 35 indicators which are again split into seven components each consisting of five indicators. The components along with the indicators are depicted in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5 : GCI

2.6 Global Soft Power Index (GSPI)

American political scientist and Harvard Professor, Joseph Nye, introduced the concept of ‘soft power’ in 1990. The main paradigm highlights that alternative methods of foreign policy without the use of force may provide better results for nation building. Soft power index defines the strength of a nation through some special soft attitudinal means which must not include coercion or any financial benefit. This index has considered the present state of global affairs where political and military coercion becomes an important parameter to gain global attention for creation of comprehensive nation brand. The factors considered are outlined in Figure 6.

Figure 6 : GSPI

2.7 Brand Finance Nation Brand Index (BFBI)

Brand Finance measures the nation brand strength using a method that is based on royalty relief mechanism employed to ascertain global brand value based on largest corporate brands. It focuses on the parameters of soft power index in five steps rather than focusing on the components, as depicted in Figure 7 below.

Figure 7 : BFBI

2.8 The Legatum Prosperity Index (LPI)

The LPI was initiated by Legatum Institute, a UK based think tank in 2007, with the mission of ‘creating the pathway from poverty to prosperity’. It evaluates long term changes in global and national prosperity focusing on various drivers of growth and recognizing nations which have made substantive or mentionable progress. LPI defines prosperity as something much more than mere wealth or economic growth; true prosperity is when all people have the opportunity to thrive. In a prosperous society, people live in peace, free from the threat of violence, oppression, and crime. Everyone’s inherent dignity is respected; all are free to vote, to protest, and to follow their beliefs. Governing institutions in every sector act with truth and are subject to the rule of law. Also, it comprises of stable families and supportive communities that instill the values that shape the culture and build the bonds of trust needed for society to flourish through harnessing individuals’ inner obligation towards society. Thus, prosperity must be driven by an open economy that harnesses ideas and talent to foster employment, enhance productivity through technological emancipation, and ensure a sustainable growth model that can take nations out of poverty and ensure wellbeing through ensuring quality education and health as prerequisite. The indicators are organized into 12 pillars which are grouped into three domains essential to prosperity: Inclusive Societies, Open Economies, and Empowered People. Figure 8 below explains the basic pillars considered in the LPI evaluation.

Figure 8 : LPI

3. RESEARCH DESIGN

3.1 Problem Definition

The problem definition of the study can be outlined in three distinct constructions; first, it is evident that several measures of Nation Brand exist which have both similarities and dissimilarities, it is therefore important that an integrated measure be used which incorporates all dimensions using some level of standardization. Second, all measures are global as far as Bangladesh is concerned, though the theoretical dimension of nation brand building exercise considers local brand image as the foundation for global brand imagery. Third, there is no single research on brand perception of Bangladesh based on perception of Bangladesh citizens to help strategize future nation brand agenda of the nation.

3.2 Objective

The study has been undertaken to cover three distinct objectives as outlined below.

1. To develop an integrated nation brand model based on the existing eight models outlined in the literature survey.
2. Assess the brand equity of Bangladesh based on an integrated model as perceived by the citizens of the People's Republic of Bangladesh.
3. Outline possible strategies to strengthen equity of Brand Bangladesh.

3.3 Sampling

This paper tries to measure the Brand Equity of Bangladesh based on the perception of both Nonresident Bangladesh (NRB) citizens and Resident Bangladesh (RB) citizens. A total 4738 respondents were targeted of which 753 were NRB while the

rest 3985 were RB. All respondents were considered homogenous, since, the global scores do not differentiate between respondents. However, only adults (above the age of 18) were considered. In addition, analysis was not based on demographic profile since all are citizen of a single country. Rather, differences in perception regarding the various components are considered important, since strategies for nation brand equity strengthening is based on the components and the indicators.

Online survey was conducted due to COVID and a total of only 1745 responses (answered to all statements) were obtained. This constitutes 36.83% of the targeted population. In addition, NRB response was 227 (30.15%), while the rest 1518 (38.09%) were RB.

3.4 Measuring Internal Country Brand Equity

The description outlined above implies that while various models are used to measure the brand index of nations, however, they do not necessarily measure the same thing and therefore it is likely to give different results. This paper tried to integrate all the models into one based on the combined importance of all the components outlined. The first task was to arrive at a singular definition for the variables outlined at various levels in the models. In addition, each level has been explained based on the specific indicator/s for respective level. In addition, the weightage of each variable at various levels was ascertained based on the combined importance of all the models outlined above.

To ensure that each resultant level has equal importance, the number of indicators representing the level has been kept equal and selected based on the outcome of the 8 models discussed above. Finally, each of the indicator was independently evaluated based on primary online survey using 7-point Likert scale to arrive at indicator score. To ensure that the overall score is indicative of the integrated model, weights are assigned based on the outcome of the integration and final equity score calculated accordingly. Since it was online survey and open-ended perception was difficult to gather, an open ended space was provided for comments. The detailed illustration of the methodology is outlined for ease of understanding.

Step 1. Literature survey identifying major models and all possible levels and variables associated with nation brand equity measures (Figure 1 through Figure 8 above).

Step 2. Cluster analysis using qualitative NVivo software to illustrate the levels and variables.

Step 3. Tree mapping using NVivo to determine the weights for each of the variables within various levels and to determine the weight differences by qualitative assessment.

Step 4. Calculate the variable weights based on the above two analyses to help in measuring brand equity.

Step 5. Measure difference in perception between NRB and RB, if any, using radar chart, mean and deviation.

Step 6. Calculating mean to measure importance for each of the variable across levels to outline score.

Step 7. Measuring brand equity based on the results from the primary survey and various weights based on the cluster output.

Step 8. Evaluating the perception outcome of Bangladesh citizens and the possible position comparing with maximum possible value achievement.

Step 9. Outline strategic direction to strengthen the brand equity of Bangladesh at various utility level intervention.

4. FINDINGS

The findings of the study are discussed based on the three distinct objectives outlined earlier. The first is to develop an integrated model, the second is the perception of Bangladesh citizens regarding brand Bangladesh based on the integrated model followed by delineating the strategic direction.

4.1 Integrated Nation Brand Model

The model categorizes three levels of factors or dependent variables, *dimension, wellbeing, components* and independent variables as *utility variables*.

From the eight models, a total of 26 components and 115 distinct utility factors were identified. However, it had duplication in terms of the definition and conceptual parameter of some of the components as well as utility factors. Thus, data cleaning was considered essential to ensure that a logical framework based on the earlier models could be developed. This required selection of an appropriate conceptual framework, and as such the concept of nation wellbeing surfaced (White, 2008) and was used as a starting point. The rationale of using wellbeing entails from the recent global acceptance of the fact that economic security, growth and material prosperity alone cannot create sustainable nations, economic performance should be seen more as means to human prosperity, not the end itself (Stiglitz et al., 2009). However, it is also important to note that, though, wellbeing as the outcome is being used at all levels, it is also considered to be extremely complex. Thus, one must clearly define the components of wellbeing to be able to measure them.

In clarifying the concept, the components of the wellbeing have been segregated to reduce the level of obscurity embedded in wellbeing; as such, in terms of clarity it has been described in terms of, *Relational Dimension*, which is an outcome that is dependent on the interrelationship between various factors and players operating within a society; *Subjective Dimension*, which represents emotional features of individuals that carve societies; and *Material Dimension*, which represents clear measurable dimensions that reflects achievement of societies” (White, 2018).

Four major wellbeing criteria have been identified based on the dimensions mentioned above, ***Social Wellbeing*** (Bakar et al., 2015) outlining the basic need of health, education, security, etc.; along with ***Natural Wellbeing*** (Sustainable Society Foundation, 2012), focusing on the environmental and planet parameters; these two are part of the relational dimension since they also relate to the overall societal norms that are outcome of interrelationship between every single player within a community. ***Human Wellbeing*** (Horlings et al., 2019), which is more to do with the individualistic people emotions and beliefs and thus part of the subjective dimension and finally ***Economic Wellbeing*** (Council of the European Union, 2019), which is clearly the material dimension highlighting the economic return due to nation brand.

The Cluster analysis involving clarity of each variable under each level was undertaken using reduction method to minimize the number of variables and delineate each of the variable for later measure involving perception mapping through primary survey of Bangladesh citizens. As indicated earlier, literature survey identified 26 components and 115 utility factors. Thus, the outcome of cluster analysis ensured more meaningful, measurable and adequate variables. Figure 9 illustrates the outcome of the detailed NVivo based qualitative cluster analysis which has 3 dimensions, 4 wellbeing indicators, 12 components and 36 utility variables. The number of utilities was reduced to three each for each of the 12 components to ensure some level of similarity and to ensure some degree of standardization. The definition of each of variables for all levels is outlined in annexure 1. For the purpose of consistency, items under each level, that is; dimension, wellbeing, component, and utility, the term variable has been used.

Figure 9 : Brand Measure Variable Decision Tree

4.2 Analyzing Distribution using Tree Map

Next analysis was conducted to determine importance of utility factor outlined in Figure 9 above which ultimately resulted in determination of the weight or importance of each dimension based on the comprehensive literature review using NVivo based distribution, Figures 10a through 10d illustrates the importance of the various concepts and constructs.

The results of NVivo severed from the normal belief that material dimension is considered important. Interestingly, Relational Dimension is considered the most important followed by Subjective Dimension and Material Dimension has least importance. Though, in Bangladesh we have been putting more importance on Material Dimension. In addition, in terms of the Wellbeing factor, Social and Human Wellbeing are considered far more important compared to Economic and Environmental Wellbeing though countries such as Bangladesh have been putting more importance on the latter two. At the component level however, Education and Research, followed Business and Investment followed by People and values hold top three position. This clearly implies that at a more micro level, variables associated with Economic Wellbeing and thus Material Dimension have importance. Though Relational Dimension and Social Wellbeing are still considered significant. At the ultimate micro level, that is utility level, Market Attraction, which is ultimately part of Material Dimension takes precedence over the rest. This indicates that while Nation Brand Building is a macro strategic approach, nations may get carried away at the utility level without giving due importance to the overall outcome outlined under nation brand building purpose.

4.3 Calculating weights for level of Variables

The weights for each of the variable under each of the level is outlined in Table 1 below.

Dimension	Weight	Wellbeing	Weight	Component	Weight	Utility	Weight
Relational Dimension	5.3	Social Wellbeing	4.1	Governance & Public Trust	1.1	Public Trust	0.46
						Autocracy	0.29
						Transparency	0.33
				Media Power	0.5	Media Reach	0.10
						Media Positivity	0.23
						Media Trust	0.16
				Education and Research	1.4	Knowledge Creation	0.50
						Knowledge Dissemination	0.62
						Knowledge advancement	0.33
				Peace and Security	0.5	Internal Conflict	0.10
						Political Stability	0.10
						Law and Order	0.20
		Health and Nutrition	0.9	Health Inclusivity	0.40		
				Access to Health	0.33		
				Life Expectancy	0.16		
		Natural Wellbeing	1.2	Heritage and Culture	0.8	Heritage Site	0.36
Global Event	0.16						
Cultural Uniqueness	0.26						
Planet and Environment	0.5			Pollution Management	0.13		
				Climate Change	0.30		
				Planet Safety	0.13		
Subjective Dimension	2.8	Human Wellbeing	1.9	Tourism	0.5	Value for Money	0.10
						Range of Attraction	0.23
						Food and Lodging	0.16
				Global Order and Partnership	0.6	Global Presence	0.13
						Peace and Progress Role	0.16
						Global Relations	0.33
				People and Values	1.2	Social Security	0.62
						Civic Status	0.33
						Cultural Openness	0.29
Material Dimension	1.9	Economic Wellbeing	2.8	Business and Investment	1.3	Market Attraction	0.66
						Resource Mobilization	0.30
						Economic Growth	0.39
				Exports and Immigration	0.7	Productivity and Quality	0.29
						Technology Adaptation	0.23
						Time Management	0.13
Total	10.0		10.0		10.0		10.0

The sum of the weight at each level is considered 100% to ensure internal consistency and to assess the importance of each variable within respective level. Table 1 indicates that as high as 53% weight is placed on relationship dimension while the material dimension comprises of only 19% weight. Though, as a nation, governments ignore the relationship dimension which may seriously impact the brand equity rating.

However, when looked at wellbeing point of view, though social wellbeing holds 41% weight, economic wellbeing is also important holding 28% weightage. This also implies that developed nations put more emphasis on factors that are more conducive towards their rating. For example, though they contribute much more in terms of environmental pollution, especially in case of creation of carbon footprint, the importance on natural wellbeing is the least at 12%.

As one moves to more micro level assessment, example if wellbeing dimension is further analyzed; two components surface, education and research (14%) and governance and public trust (11%). One each component, business and investment (13%) and people and values (12%) surface as part of economic and human

wellbeing. This clearly implies that while relational wellbeing had major share of weightage; however, national strategy at the micro level must be adjusted to seek global presence.

At the utility level, only 4 utilities out of the 36 have more than 5% weightage points, market attraction (6.6%), social relations (6.2%), knowledge dissemination (6.2%), and knowledge creation (5%). Clearly, larger markets such as China, India in terms of population size and developed economy having greater purchasing power are likely to win the race. Also, knowledge plays a very important role along with basic social security. Thus, nations must focus on education and unique market creation (blue ocean or unique offerings), to be able to successfully create a brand image.

4.4 Measuring difference between perception of NRB and RB

Figures 11 below depicts the difference regarding various utility factors as perceived by the Nonresident Bangladeshi and Resident Bangladeshi. Unlike the initial observation, where all respondents were considered homogenous, since, the global scores do not differentiate between respondents. The results clearly indicate that even within the two groups under study, NRB and RB, based on the outcome of the perception of respondents under the primary survey, there is a huge difference in perception. A 7-point Likert scale was used to measure level of agreement. 7 was considered strongly agree while 1 was considered as strongly disagree. Thus, depending on the statement, utility variables below, 4 are considered below par. Out of the 36 utility variables, according to all the respondents inclusive of deviation; 14 were positive, 13 neutral, and the rest 9 weaknesses. This implies that Bangladesh according to the Bangladeshi citizens have a good opportunity to be a brand as far as the perception is concerned.

Figure 11 : Mapping Difference Between Nonresident Bangladeshi (NRB) and Resident Bangladeshi (RB)

Out of the total of 36 utility variables considered in the study, 19 were statistically significantly different while 17 were found to be having similar perception. This indicates that even within the Bangladeshi citizenry, under the classification of resident and nonresident, similar strategies to strengthen nation brand building intervention is unlikely to work. The detailed finding is presented in annexure 2.

4.5 Qualitative Analysis

The findings based on the perception score of utility variables as outlined in annexure 2 indicate that out of 36 variables, 10 have positive scores, 7 have negative scores, while the rest 19 are more or less neutral. The qualitative analysis of the 12 component variables is outlined below.

1. Governance and Public Trust: The perception of NRB and RB regarding 'public trust' and 'autocracy' are similar while regarding 'transparency' there is a significant difference. Regarding transparency and autocracy, though both have a fairly neutral opinion, however, the RB consider greater transparency. The concern is in public trust; this is a major concern which to a certain extent contradicts the results of other two utility factors. Interestingly, the level of trust amongst RB is less compared to the NRB.
2. Media Power: The perception of the two groups regarding 'media reach' and 'media trust' are significantly different in terms of the weights assigned. Media reach for example is considered strong by both but the RB consider this to be much stronger compared to NRB. On the other hand, media trust of NRB is positive while that of RB is neutral. The area of concern in this component is 'positivity of media' regarding building Bangladesh perception, both have equally negative opinion regarding the role of media in building the image of Bangladesh.
3. Education and Research: According to both groups, academia is weak in 'creation of knowledge' which is part of research and innovation while are strong in terms of teaching and learning representing 'knowledge dissemination'. However, regarding 'advancement of knowledge' beyond the boundaries of Bangladesh, the NRB have a neutral opinion while the RB consider this to be somewhat positive.
4. Peace and Security: Regarding existence of internal 'political conflict' both consider this to be of some concern, however, the NRB consider this to be a much graver issue compared to RB. Interestingly however, both consider that the country is 'politically stable', though RB consider it more stable compared to NRB. Regarding 'law and order' situation, the response is neutral, implying they are neither satisfied nor too much dissatisfied.
5. Health and Nutrition: Interestingly, this component has greater acceptability. The NRB are neutral regarding 'inclusivity' and 'access to health' while the RB are satisfied with the general health management of the country. Both consider hygiene, maternal health and public health offerings to be good resulting in greater 'life expectancy'.

6. Heritage and Culture: The general perception is that Bangladesh has a strong 'heritage' and 'cultural uniqueness'. However, though RB consider global 'cultural events' to be reasonably strong, the NRB have a neutral opinion, implying it is not enough.
7. Planet and Environment: Both groups consider environment as a threat for Bangladesh, particularly when considering the impact of 'climate change'. Moreover, the NRB consider 'planet safety' issue to be a threat for the country. Both are neutral regarding steps taken by the nation to tackle climate change and are extremely negative regarding issues pertaining to maintaining a better planet through 'pollution management'.
8. Tourism: Tourism potential has a neutral to strong perception. The satisfaction level of the RB is far greater compared to the NRB. The major strength considered by both is 'food and lodging' followed by 'value for money' and 'range of attraction'.
9. Global Order and Partnership: The level of acceptability as a global nation is also acceptable. While role in maintaining global 'peace and progress' is considered strong by both, the RB consider it substantive through participation in peace keeping force and Rohingya attention. However, both consider that more could be done in terms of strengthening 'global relations' through greater value addition and thus increasing 'global presence'.
10. People and Values: Although both groups consider 'cultural openness' to be a strong point for Bangladesh, more could be done to strengthen 'social security'. Also, though RB are happy with the 'civic status', NRB consider that much more should be done to improve the civic condition in general.
11. Business and Investment: This component is considered as one of the major strengths of the country. Both groups are happy with the 'economic growth' and consider 'market as attractive', for investment. However, the RB are not very happy with the efforts placed for resource mobilization although resource in terms of human capital as well as financial and technical resources are available.
12. Exports and Immigration: Though 'productivity and quality' of both goods as well as services are considered good by both the groups; improvements in 'technology adaptation' is sought by both groups, nevertheless it is considered as a thrust sector by the government. The major concern is in 'time management', which is one of the major concerns for ease of doing business in Bangladesh.

4.6 Measuring Brand Equity

Brand equity has been measured using the weights obtained for the 'Dimension variables', 'Wellbeing variables', 'Components variables' and 'Utility variables' as outlined in table 1 and the perception scores obtained for the various 'utility variables' from the primary survey. Mean values are used from perception survey since the objective was to obtain a general understanding of the internal brand equity outcome for Bangladesh.

Figure 12 depicts that Bangladesh, as perceived by the internal market, are performing almost the same in all three of dimension variables. However, unlike the global perception outlined in the literature survey (Bhuiyan, 2021), the internal perception outweighs global perception. In general, global perception indices have placed Bangladesh around 50 percentile which is 15 percentiles lower compared to the internal perception mean brand equity score of 65.29%.

Fig 12 : Bangladesh Equity Percentile Score for Dimension Variables

At the next level of wellbeing variable analysis, as depicted in figure 13 below, the results as expected from the macro analysis far better the results at the global level. The equity scores according to strength is as follows: Natural – 67.55% and Human – 66.03% are statistically same. Finally, Social – 60.43% and Economic 56.83% are statistically significantly lower compared to the rest of the two variables.

Fig 13 : Bangladesh Equity Percentile Score for Wellbeing Variables

Further analysis of the 12-component level brand equity score of each of the variable is depicted in Figure 14 below. Two major areas of concern which are below 50 percentile points ‘planet and environment’ and more importantly perhaps ‘governance and public trust’. ‘Education and research’ just made it above 50 percentile point and

is another concern area. The areas of strengths are clearly ‘media power’, ‘heritage and culture’, as expected, ‘business and investment’ and to a certain extent ‘tourism’. The rest of the six variables also have opportunity for improvement. The results imply that although at the more macro level, it seems Bangladesh is doing well, however, closer look has identified some major potholes that must be mended to ensure sustainable growth.

Fig 14 : Bangladesh Equity Percentile Score for Component Variables

The results in Figure 14 clearly calls for closer look to target specific areas outlined in the 36 distinct utility variables to design a strategic intervention for both equity score enhancement as well as to ensure sustainable growth of the nation. Figure 15 outlines the equity score of all 36 utility variables.

Figure 15 : Bangladesh Equity Percentile Score for Utility Variable

The results outlined in Figure 15 and Annexure 3 can be summarized through creation of three categories of utility variables. The first are the strengths of Bangladesh which have scored a score of around 70 percentiles. These include a total of 12 (33%) variables; media reach, knowledge dissemination, political stability, life expectancy, heritage sites, cultural uniqueness, climate change initiative, value for money in tourism, food and lodging for tourists, participation in global peace and progress, cultural openness, market attraction, and economic growth. The second group are the mediocre performing variables which can be easily worked at for improvement and are those which have scored between 55 to less than 70 percentile scores. They constitute 17 (47%) variables; autocracy, transparency, media trust, knowledge advancement, internal conflict, political stability, health inclusivity, access to health, global cultural event, planet safety initiative, range of tourist attraction, global presence, global relations, civic status, resource mobilization, productivity and quality, and technology adaptation. The last group are the concern areas for Bangladesh with a score of 55 percentile or less. This comprise of 7 (20%) variables; public trust, lack of media positivity, knowledge creation, law and order, pollution management, social security, and time management.

4.7 Strategic Intervention Model

Based on the results outlined and the detailed analysis the following specific strategic interventions can be proposed against each of the utility variables. It is obvious that measures at the utility level is likely to create a positive impact at the more macro level. The strategic recommendation is discussed based on the three levels of intervention, viz, areas of strength, mediocre performing variables, and finally the weak links.

4.7.1 Strategies for Areas of Strength

As discussed above a total of 12 utility variables provide the major positive equity score for Bangladesh. Of these 12, economic growth and life expectancy due to adequate nutrition and public health measures at the bottom of the pyramid is well recognized at the global level. At the same time, these two are likely to taper soon, which implies importance must be shifted and continue with a maintenance strategy for these two variables, however, since the economic growth and life expectancy are positive, new market creation is evident with greater opportunities for investments and global partnership mobilization. The results further indicate that Bangladesh is not only rich in heritage and culture, but at the same time, the country is both unique in many ways and is open to new cultural quintessence. In addition, the infrastructure for tourism is considered good which implies that the country should put extra emphasis on the tourism sector, especially in bringing in foreign tourists through utilization of media, which has a good reach. One of the major global presence of Bangladesh is in the global peace keeping forces, this is also evident in the results of the research. Thus, media should also focus on this very important global uniqueness embedded within the strategic strength of Bangladesh. The strength in knowledge dissemination implies that any awareness drive focusing on knowledge and beyond

is likely to bear positive result. In addition, since knowledge dissemination is directly associated with the young generation of the country, the opportunity to further educate the youth is very promising provided the correct knowledge is channeled through these knowledge outlets.

Figure 16 : Model for Strengths of Bangladesh Brand Equity

Figure 16 above depicts the nation brand equity model for determining the strengths of brand Bangladesh. Figure indicates that the strengths reach is up to the component level, implying though the country depicts 12 areas of utility variables as strengths, however the other variables outweigh the reach. Moreover, out of the total 12 component variables only 4 have been reached through utility strength variables. However, three distinct component variables should be focused by Bangladesh, business & investment, heritage & culture and tourism. The media reach can aid in further strengthening the brand equity, provided it is used with due diligence.

4.7.2 Strategies for Areas of Mediocrity

A total of 17 or 47% represent this category. The scores are representative of the present day overall score that Bangladesh has been attaining in various models. One of the most important parameters of middle order scores is the danger of falling into mediocrity trap. The first and foremost mediocrity is in the realm of governance which clearly is one major focus of mediocrity trap. Governance to large extent is a result of mediocrity in internal conflict and political stability. Media trust though relative, does contribute towards creation of mediocrity mindset of the population at large. Health and education are a clear indicator of not pursuing to reach the next level due to mediocrity in knowledge and thus clearly not pursuing the strategies to build a knowledge economy, which requires, strengthening research and innovation drive. The utility variables such as organizing global events, strengthening global relations, global presence, and ensuring multiple tourist attraction are physical evidence of excellence and in absence of these mediocrity supersedes. Also, the global competitiveness increases with emphasis on such utility variables. It is also easier to implement these compared to other variables. Resource enhancement,

productivity enhancement, and technology adaptation are directly correlated with elements of knowledge creation and knowledge advancement. Thus, any lapses in focus of knowledge economy will result in mediocrity trap for these utility factors. Ensuring planet safety and strengthening of civic status of citizens in general perhaps calls for fulfilling all the mediocrity trap utility variable discussed earlier. One other important issue should be considered, aging population and narrowing of demographic dividend. Thus, appropriate skills and human values must be inculcated now to reap the benefits in the future.

Figure 17 below depicts the brand equity model for variables determining mediocrity profile of brand Bangladesh. The scores indicate that Bangladesh at the core of Brand Equity is considered as a mediocre nation, which is quite reasonable since the nation is just now graduating from a least developed nation to a middle-income nation. However, the basic concern is the move to the next level. The middle-income nations represent 75% of the world population but at the same time, constitute 62% of the world poor. This is the contention of middle-income trap (Bulman et al., 2017). Thus, over the years, only a handful of nations have been able to move up the ladder.

Figure 17 : Mediocrity Model of Bangladesh Brand Equity Strength Determination

Thus, Bangladesh must look at the variables that result in creation of this trap. Results indicate that at the component level the major variables are, health and nutrition, people and values, global order and partnership, export and immigration, finally, peace and security. It implies that an acceptable level in all these areas have been achieved but the next level requires greater effort. A greater focus indicates that for health and nutrition, the nation should focus more on health inclusivity and thus access to health at the lower end of the economy. This is also related to enhancement of public health in general to strengthen civic responsibility of people which is likely to strengthen value dimension of people. Thus, this calls for communicating awareness to change the mindset of greater population. To achieve the above, global

partnership and adaptation of global model in the context of Bangladesh is necessary. Furthermore, although Bangladesh has scored high in economic growth, but the overall score on economic wellbeing remains mediocre. This is mainly due to low productivity of workforce in general and adaptation of technology. Bangladesh has been focusing on labor cost as a competitive advantage, but with the 4th industrial revolution, taking the world by force, gears need to be changed. Last but not the least, peace and security within a middle-income economy has always been contentious and Bangladesh is no exception. This is where more open mindedness along with 'Nation First for Global Harmony' attitude needs to be embodied. A common political vision must be the driving force. Bangladesh has returned to the growth track in the last decade primarily because of this common understanding and appreciation being embedded that we have fought a war for freedom under the leadership of our Father of the Nation, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman and we are a pluralistic nation. To be able to proceed further, cherishing this united effort is essential and at the same time, a more democratic political thought process must be entertained. The rest of the utility variables though important are less impacting the core wellbeing and dimension variables.

The mediocrity trap is further evident in Figure 17 from the outcome, showing that the impact is from the utility level to the core level of dimension. All three dimensions and all four wellbeing variables have a mediocre perception. This is where the nation must commit to work beyond the material dimension and economic wellbeing and must put focus on the other variables.

4.7.3 Strategies for Areas of Weakness

Figure 18 shows that the weakness of brand Bangladesh is represented by 7 utility variables and 3 component variables. Though apparently the core variables are not considered as weaknesses, however, it is apparent that the core values are to a large extent impacted due to these weaknesses. The weakness in planet and environment is acceptable while considering climate change but is unacceptable once pollution management is considered a major concern. Similarly, it is evident that though knowledge dissemination is a strength, however, tertiary level education is not putting emphasis on research and innovation. In addition, the negativity of media clearly indicates why awareness of people regarding positive dimensions of the nation and its role in awareness building in general is perhaps lacking. The major focus however should be on governance and public trust, which is a result of low public trust on the nation. This is perhaps the most important outcome of the study. Time management is again an issue of productivity and law and order more of a perception to be sorted out through good governance.

Figure 18 : Model for Weaknesses of Bangladesh Brand Equity

5. CONCLUSION, LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH AGENDA

5.1 Conclusion

In 1947 Simon Kuznets, an economist, presented the concept of Gross Domestic Product or GDP in his famous report, “National Income, 1929-35”. Since then, GDP has been considered by most as the measure of nations overall welfare, an indicator of the soul of an economy, and of course the ultimate Nobel winning statistical indicator of nations health. However, over recent times, it gradually became apparent that GDP could not be trusted to measure the overall health of a nation resulting in the welfare of her citizens. The latest concept of Social Progress Index led by Michael Green focuses on social and environmental needs. Countries and even companies adopting the above are likely to have an edge because they can combine a quality promise with a mission imbued with positive values.

To achieve the next level Bangladesh must focus on the above principle of growth, put more emphasis on subjective and relational dimensions and along with ensuring a wellbeing attitude in all activities rather than just economic growth. At the operational level, the utility variables must be considered by all stakeholders including the general citizens of the country. At the strategic level, the components should be the focus. In addition, strengths must take the scores to 80s, which is likely to be difficult and requires all to focus on perfection and excellence. The mediocre utility variables are something that requires more of changing mindset and should be outlined in every single short-term plan of the nation as well as organizations. The weaknesses must be embedded within the policy framework of government and seriously delved into. There was no theoretical work before for measuring internal nation brand equity of Bangladesh. This paper will help academicians and researchers to take the research of internal brand equity to the next level. Combining all these eight models to measure internal national brand equity is the unique contribution of this study.

5.2 Limitation of the Study

The study considered eight nation brand equity index which may not be exhaustive and may entail differences in terms of approach. The weightage used is based on the outcome of the global indices analysis and thus may not represent the weight that could have been assigned by the sampling frame. The study was undertaken during COVID and thus stress factor may have influenced the rating by the respondents. The study has assumed that the difference between NRB and RB is negligible though the findings have shown statistical difference. Thus, the final mean scores do have an element of standard deviation. Since the study was online, the actual respondent is difficult to ascertain. The study took almost a year to complete, therefore, the response period is staggered and not within a limited time frame. Since the variables are exhaustive, a clear comparison with any single model that are in practice is difficult. The research did not consider validation of the data collected; thus, the primary survey results are considered final.

5.3 Future Research Agenda

The concept of brand equity is very much needed to be inbuilt in the national activities and future planning. Future study can be undertaken in the developing and underdeveloped world to identify weights for each of the variable. Future research should include a third category, the expatriates. Future research can explore to establish a model based on objective behavior beyond perceptual measures. In fact, we also think it is possible to use these measures to assess brand equity of other countries and perhaps create a nation brand equity index. Research may also be undertaken to assess differences between various segments along with geographical location. A post COVID research can be conducted to assess stress related impact. Research on the specific issues of the nation brand building with an intent to translate the more strategic dimension outlined in this research to operational level may be conducted.

REFERENCES

- Aaker, D. (1991). "Managing Brand Equity", Free Press, New York.
- Abramovitz, M. (1959). "The Allocation of Economic Resources", *Economics, Stanford Studies in History, Economics, and Political Science*, Volume 17, Stanford University Press.
- Anand, S. and Sen, A. (1994). "Human Development Index: Methodology and Measurement", *Human Development Occasional Papers*, Volume 2, United Nations Development Programme.
- Anholt, S. (1998). "Nation Brands of the Twenty-first Century", *Journal of Brand Management*, Volume 5, Issue 6, pp 395-406.
- Anholt, S. (2002). "Nation Branding: A Continuing Theme", *Journal of Brand Management*, Volume 10, Number 1, 2002, pp 59-60.
- Anholt, S. (2008). "Place Branding: Is it Marketing or isn't it?" *Place Branding and Public Diplomacy*, 4, 1, p1.
- Anwar, S. F. (2010). "Branding Bangladesh: Importance of Political Vision", *Amcham: Journal of American Chamber of Commerce in Bangladesh*, Volume 3, Number 1.
- Anwar, S. F. (2018). "Building a Nation Brand," *The Daily Star*, February 2018.
- Bakar, A. A., Osman, M. M., Bachok, S., Ibrahim, M. and Mohamed, M. Z. (2015). "Modelling Economic and Social Wellbeing for Sustainability: A Theoretical Concept", *Procedia Environmental Science*, Volume 28, pp 286-296.
- The Legatum Prosperity Index (2021), Legatum Institute, London, United Kingdom.
- Baru, S. (1998). "Mahbub ul Haq and Human Development: A Tribute", *Economic and Political Weekly*, Volume 33, Number 35, pp 2275-2279.
- Bastos, W. and Levy, S. J. (2012). "A History of the Concept of Branding: Practices and Theory", *Journal of Historical Research in Marketing*, Volume 4, Issue 3, pp 351-357.
- Bhuiyan, M. (2021). Bangladesh has Poor Brand Value as a Nation, *The Business Standard*.
- Brand Finance (2010). "The Future Brand Index", *A Unique Country Perception Study*, November 2020.
- Brand Finance (2021). "Global Soft Power Index", Perceptions of Nation Brands.
- Bulman, D., Eden, M. and Nguyen, H. (2017). "Transition from Low Income Growth to High Income Growth: Is there a Middle-Income Trap?", *ADB Working Paper Series*, Number 646.
- Butler, R. S. (1914). "Marketing Methods," Alexander Hamilton Institute, New York.

- Council of the European Union (2019). "The Economy of Wellbeing", OECD paper on *creating opportunities for people's wellbeing and economic growth*, Brussels.
- Dinnie, K. (2004). "Place Branding: Overview of an Emerging Literature", *Place Branding*, Volume 1, Issue 1, pp 106-110.
- Dinnie, K. (2015). *Nation Branding: Concept, Issues, Practice*, Routledge, London, 2nd Edition.
- Dolores, M., Garcia, D., Horlings, L., Swagemakers, P., and Fernandez, X. S. (2013). "Place Branding and Endogenous Rural Development. Departure Points for Developing an Inner Brand of the River Minho Estuary," *Place Branding and Public Diplomacy*, 9, 2, pp 124-140.
- East West Communications (2019). "Nation Brand Perception Indexes". Retrieved from www.eastwestcoms.com/global.htm on May 2022.
- Fan, Y. (2006). "Branding the Nation: What is Being Branded", *Journal of Vacation Marketing*, Volume 12, Issue 1, pp 5-14.
- Fan, Y. (2010). "Branding the Nation: Towards a Better Understanding", *Place Branding and Public Diplomacy*, Volume 6, pp 97-103.
- Feinberg, B. F. and Zhao, X. (2021). "The Anholt-GfK Roper Nation Brand Index: Navigating the Changing World", *International Place Branding Yearbook*, Springer, Palgrave Macmillan, pp 63-77.
- Fetscherin, M. (2010). "The Determinants and Measurement of a Country Brand: The Country Brand Strength Index", *International Marketing Review*, Volume 27, Issue 4, pp 466-479.
- Future Brand Country Index (2019). <https://www.futurebrand.com/uploads/FCI/FutureBrand-Country-Index-2019.pdf>. Retrieved on May 2022.
- Good Country Index (2021). <http://www.index.goodcountry.org>. Retrieved from May 2022.
- Harengel, P. and Gbadamosi, A. (2014). "Launching A New Nation: The Unfolding Brand of South Sudan", *Place Branding and Public Diplomacy*, Volume 10, Number 1, pp 35-54.
- Gusfield, J. (1978). "Community: A Critical Response", Harper & Row, New York.
- Haigh, D. (2020). "Nation Brands: The annual report on the most valuable and strongest nation brands", *Brand Finance*, November 2020.
- Horlings, E. and Smits, J. (2019). "Measuring Wellbeing and Sustainability in the Netherlands: The First Monitor of Wellbeing", *ESCoE Conference on Economic Measurement*, King's College London.
- Ikalafeng, T. (2010). "Why Brand a Nation?" *Design Indaba: A Better World Through Creativity*, South Africa.

Kagan, J., Boyle, M. J. and Kvilhaug, S. (2021). "Gross National Happiness (GNH)?"', *Economy, Government, and Policy*, Investopedia.

Keller, K. L. (2003). "Strategic Brand Management: Building, Measuring, and Managing Brand Equity", New Jersey, Prentice-Hall, 2003.

Kotler, P., Kartajaya, H., and Setiawan, I. (2010). "Marketing 3.0: From Products to Customers to Human Spirit", John Wiley and Sons, Inc.

Kuznets, S. (1947). "Quantitative Aspects of the Economic Growth of Nations: X. Level and Structure of Foreign Trade: Long Term Trends", *Economic Development and Cultural Change*, Volume 15, Number 2, Part 2.

Lasch, C. (1991). "The True and Only Heaven: Progress and its Critics, New York.

Marshall, G. (1994). "The Concise Oxford Dictionary of Sociology, Oxford University Press, Oxford.

Moore, K. and Reid, S. (2008). "The Birth of Brand: 4000 Years of Branding", *Business History*, Volume 50, Issue 4, pp 422-424.

Nye, J. S. (1990). "Soft Power", *Foreign Policy*, Number 80, pp 153-171.

Olins, W. (2002). "Branding the Nation-The Historical Context", *Journal of Brand Management*, Volume 9, Issue 4-5, pp 241-248.

Peter, F. (1989). "Managing Brand Equity", *Marketing Research*, Volume 1, pp 24-33.

Rashid, B. (2013). "Conceptualization of Nation Brand Image", *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, Volume 20, Issue 1, pp 165-183.

Roth, M. S. (1995). "The Effects of Culture and Socioeconomics on the Performance of Global Brand Image Strategies," *Journal of Marketing Research*, Volume 32, Issue 5, 1995, pp 163-175.

Simon, C. J. and Sullivan, M. W. (1993). "The Measurement and Determinants of Brand Equity: A Financial Approach", *Marketing Science*, Volume 12, Issue 1, pp 28-52.

Sustainable Society Foundation (2012). "Measuring Wellbeing and Progress Towards Sustainability: Beyond GDP". *The Hague September*. Retrieved from www.ssfindex.com on May 2022.

Stiglitz, J., Sen, A. and Fitoussi, J.P. (2009). "Report by the commission on the measurement of economic performance and social progress". Retrieved from www.stiglitz-sen-fitoussi.fr on May 2022.

Teslik, L. H. (2007). "Nation Branding Explained," *Council on Foreign Relations*.

Tonnies, F. (1957). *Gemeinschaft und Gesellschaft*, translated by Charles P. Loomis, (original article 1887), East Lansing: Michigan State University Press.

White, S. C. (2008). “But What is Wellbeing? A Framework for Analysis in Social and Development Policy and Practice”, BATH, UK : ESRC Research Group on Wellbeing in Developing Countries.

White, C. S. (2018). “Coastal Fishing Towns of Cromer and Sheringham, Norfolk UK: Implication for Social Wellbeing”, in book *Social Wellbeing and the Values of Small-Scale Fisheries*, pp 45-74.

Yavuzasian, K. and Cetin, M. (2016). “Soft Power Concept and Soft Power Indexes”, *Business Challenges in the Changing Economic Landscape*, volume 1, pp 395-409.